

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Ceres Science HAMO (CSH) (vir_da704)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da704 session. These operations were executed as part of the CSH phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Ceres, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da704 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis et al., "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_csh_C5HAMO.r16.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_csh_C5HAMO.r16.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
□	□	✓	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
✓	□	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_csh_C5HAMO.r16.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CSH_YMLSTART_C5HAMO	496951321	496951323	2
VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001	496951381	496954419	3038
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_001	496954419	496965225	10806
VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001	496965230	496967044	1814
VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig6Gb_001	496967329	496967341	12
VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_001	496967449	496967489	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001	496967569	496977453	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_001	496977513	496977551	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_001	496977633	496977640	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_001	496977753	496985853	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_001	496985853	496985974	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_002	497024573	497035379	10806
VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_002	497035433	497035473	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002	497035553	497045437	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_002	497045497	497045535	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_002	497045617	497045624	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_002	497045737	497053837	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_002	497053837	497053958	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_003	497092552	497103358	10806
VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_003	497103412	497103452	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003	497103532	497112376	8844
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_003	497113476	497113514	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_003	497113596	497113603	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_003	497113716	497121816	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_003	497121816	497121937	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_004	497160527	497171333	10806
VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_004	497171387	497171427	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004	497171507	497181391	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_004	497181451	497181489	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_004	497181571	497181578	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_004	497181691	497189791	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_004	497189791	497189912	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_005	497228497	497239303	10806
VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_005	497239357	497239397	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005	497239477	497249361	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_005	497249421	497249459	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_005	497249541	497249548	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_005	497249661	497257761	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_005	497257761	497257882	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_006	497296470	497307276	10806

VIR_CSH_C5openCover_006	497307330	497307370	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006	497307450	497317334	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_006	497317394	497317432	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_006	497317514	497317521	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_006	497317634	497325734	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_006	497325734	497325855	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_007	497364449	497375255	10806
VIR_CSH_C5openCover_007	497375309	497375349	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007	497375429	497385313	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_007	497385373	497385411	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_007	497385493	497385500	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_007	497385613	497393713	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_007	497393713	497393834	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_008	497432432	497443238	10806
VIR_CSH_C5openCover_008	497443292	497443332	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008	497443412	497453296	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_008	497453356	497453394	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_008	497453476	497453483	7
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_008	497453596	497461696	8100
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_008	497461696	497461817	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_009	497500414	497511220	10806
VIR_CSH_C5openCover_009	497511274	497511314	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009	497511394	497521278	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_009	497521338	497521376	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_009	497521458	497521465	7
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_009	497521578	497521699	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_010	497568390	497579196	10806
VIR_CSH_C5openCover_010	497579250	497579290	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010	497579370	497589254	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_010	497589314	497589352	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_010	497589434	497589441	7
VIR_CSH_C5PartialDumpDataToVR4_010	497589554	497596754	7200
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_010	497598564	497598685	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_011	497636363	497647169	10806
VIR_CSH_C5openCover_011	497647223	497647263	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011	497647343	497657227	9884
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_011	497657287	497657325	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_011	497657407	497657414	7
VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_011	497657527	497657648	121
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_012	497704337	497715143	10806
VIR_CSH_C5openCover_012	497715197	497715237	40
VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012	497715317	497722481	7164
VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_012	497725261	497725299	38
VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_012	497725381	497725388	7

VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_012	497725501	497725622	121
VIR_CSH_C5Standby_012	497855881	497855886	5
VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_012	497855941	497888341	32400
VIR_CSH_VMLEND_C5HAMO	497888401	497888402	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Integrated sequence: da704e.00.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da704e.00.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 84 cubes for IR channel and 0 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

3. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

3.1 The sequence: vir_csh_C5HAMO.r16.sasf

```

1   CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2   MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3   SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4   DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5   FILE_NAME = vir_csh_C5HAMO.r16.sasf;
6   APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2015-227T00:00:00.000;
7   APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2015-300T00:00:00.000;
8   PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2015-264T13:36:44.000;
9   PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10  SEQ_ID = vir_csh_C5HAMO.r16;
11  HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12  CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13  $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14  *****
15  *PROJECT    DWN
16  *SPACECRAFT 203
17  *OPERATOR   sfonte
18  *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19  *DATE       Mon Sep 21 13:36:44 2015
20  *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21  *BEGIN      2015-227T00:00:00.000
22  *CUTOFF     2015-300T00:00:00.000
23  *TITLE      VIR_CSH_da704_Cycle5_ds713
24  *EPOCHS_DEF
25  *CSH_DLTERM_057, 2015-274T06:53:33.000
26  *CSH_DLTERM_058, 2015-275T01:46:37.000
27  *CSH_DLTERM_059, 2015-275T20:39:36.000
28  *CSH_DLTERM_060, 2015-276T15:32:31.000
29  *CSH_DLTERM_061, 2015-277T10:25:21.000
30  *CSH_DLTERM_062, 2015-278T05:18:14.000
31  *CSH_DLTERM_063, 2015-279T00:11:13.000
32  *CSH_DLTERM_064, 2015-279T19:04:16.000
33  *CSH_DLTERM_065, 2015-280T13:57:18.000
34  *CSH_DLTERM_066, 2015-281T08:50:14.000
35  *CSH_DLTERM_067, 2015-282T03:43:07.000
36  *CSH_DLTERM_068, 2015-282T22:36:01.000
37  *EPOCHS_END
38  *Input files used:
39  *File Type  Last modified      File name
40  *****
41  $$EOH
42  $$EOD
43
44  request(VIR_CSH_VMLSTART_C5HAMO,
45          START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057-00:51:32,
46          TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_csh_C5HAMO (ds713)",
47          REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
48          PROCESSOR, "GSC1",

```

```
49     KEY, "No_Key")
50
51     activity(1,
52         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
53         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds713","ds713.n
54         fb04")
55     ),
56     note(1,
57         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
58         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds713 - vir_csh_C5HAMO"\
59     ),
60
61     request(VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001,
62         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057-00:50:32,
63         TITLE, "VIR Mass Memory setting to 2 Gbit",
64         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
65         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
66         KEY, "No_Key")
67
68     command(1,
69         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
70         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
71         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
72     ),
73     command(2,
74         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
75         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001: changing of MM mode into MM_PROTECTED_FULL (2 Gbit)"\",
76         VIR_TC_MM_CONF("MM_PROTECTED_FULL")
77     ),
78     command(3,
79         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
80         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001: confermation of last VIR_TC_MM_CONF(MM_PROTECTED_FULL)"\",
81         VIR_TC_CONFIRM(54)
82     ),
83     command(4,
84         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:30\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
85         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001: enter the MM in test mode"\,
86         VIR_MM_TEST()
87     ),
88     command(5,
89         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
90         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001: confermation of last VIR_MM_TEST"\,
91         VIR_TC_CONFIRM(18)
92     ),
93     note(1,
94         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:50:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
95         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig2Gb_001: VIR Mass Memory Mode is 2 Gbit protected."\"
96     ),
97     end;
98
99     request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_001,
100         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+00:00:06,
101         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
102         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
103         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
104         KEY, "No_Key")
```

```
105
106     command(1,
107         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
108         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
109         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
110     ),
111     command(2,
112         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
113         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_001: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\\,
114         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
115     ),
116     note(1,
117         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
118         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_001: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
119         waiting.\"\\
120     ),
121 end;
122 request(VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001,
123     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+03:00:17,
124     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
125     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
126     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
127     KEY, "No_Key")
128
129     command(1,
130         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
131         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY\"\\,
132         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
133     ),
134     command(2,
135         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
136         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: perform the internal full calibration\"\\,
137         VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F","CLOSECOVERATEND","FULLCALSEQ")
138     ),
139     command(3,
140         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
141         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: select VIR on 1553 bus\"\\,
142         XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT("VIR")
143     ),
144     command(4,
145         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
146         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
147         VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
148     ),
149     command(5,
150         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
151         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY\"\\,
152         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
153     ),
154     note(1,
155         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
156         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: full calibration is finished.\"\\
157     ),
158     note(2,
159         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
160         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CalibrationDump_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960
161         packets.\"\\
```

```
161     ),
162 end;
163
164 request(VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig6Gb_001,
165         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+03:35:16,
166         TITLE, "VIR Mass Memory setting to 6 Gibit",
167         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
168         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
169         KEY, "No_Key")
170
171     command(1,
172         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
173         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig6Gb_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
174         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
175     ),
176     command(2,
177         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
178         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig6Gb_001: changing of MM mode into MM_NOTPROTECTED_FULL (6 Gibit)"\,
179         VIR_TC_MM_CONF("MM_NOTPROTECTED_FULL")
180     ),
181     command(3,
182         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
183         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig6Gb_001: confermation of last
184         VIR_TC_MM_CONF(MM_NOTPROTECTED_FULL)"\,
185         VIR_TC_CONFIRM(54)
186     ),
187     note(1,
188         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
189         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5MemConfig6Gb_001: VIR Mass Memory Mode is 6 Gibit not protected."
190     ),
191 end;
192
193 request(VIR_CSH_C50penCover_001,
194         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+03:37:16,
195         TITLE, "VIR open cover",
196         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
197         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
198         KEY, "No_Key")
199
200     activity(1,
201         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
202         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C50penCover_001: Set for opening the cover."
203         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
204     ),
205 end;
206
207 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001,
208         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+03:39:16,
209         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
210         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
211         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
212         KEY, "No_Key")
213
214     command(1,
215         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
216         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
217         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
218         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
```

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217     ),
218     command(2,
219         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
220         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
                frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
221         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
222     ),
223     command(3,
224         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
226         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
227         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
228     ),
229     command(4,
230         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
231         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
232         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
233     ),
234     note(1,
235         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
236         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
237     ),
238     command(5,
239         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
240         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
                SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
241         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
242     ),
243     command(6,
244         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
245         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
                frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
246         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
247     ),
248     command(7,
249         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
250         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
251         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
252         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
253     ),
254     command(8,
255         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
256         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
257         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
258     ),
259     note(2,
260         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
261         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
262     ),
263     command(9,
264         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
265         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
                SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
266         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
267     ),
268     command(10,

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269     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
270     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
271     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
272     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
273     ),  
274     command(11,  
275     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
276     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
277     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
278     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
279     ),  
280     command(12,  
281     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
282     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
283     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
284     ),  
285     note(3,  
286     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
287     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\  
288     ),  
289     command(13,  
290     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
291     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
292     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
293     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
294     ),  
295     command(14,  
296     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
297     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
298     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
299     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
300     ),  
301     command(15,  
302     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
303     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
304     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
305     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
306     ),  
307     command(16,  
308     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
309     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
310     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
311     ),  
312     note(4,  
313     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
314     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\  
315     ),  
316     command(17,  
317     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
318     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
319     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
320     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
321     ),  
322     command(18,  
323     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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320 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
321 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
322 ),
323 command(19,
324 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
325 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
326 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
327 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
328 ),
329 command(20,
330 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:23:16\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
331 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
332 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
333 ),
334 note(5,
335 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
336 TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit\"\\
337 ),
338 command(21,
339 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
340 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
341 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
342 ),
343 command(22,
344 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
345 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
346 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
347 ),
348 command(23,
349 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
350 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
351 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
352 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
353 ),
354 command(24,
355 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:23:16\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
356 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
357 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
358 ),
359 note(6,
360 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
361 TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit\"\\
362 ),
363 command(25,
364 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
365 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
366 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
367 ),
368 command(26,
369 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
370 NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
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371     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
372 ),
373     command(27,
374     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
375     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\",\
376     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
377     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
378 ),
379     command(28,
380     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
381     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
382     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
383 ),
384     note(7,
385     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
386     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
387 ),
388 end;
389
390 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_001,
391     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+06:25:00,
392     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
393     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
394     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
395     KEY, "No_Key")
396
397     activity(1,
398     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
399     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
400     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
401 ),
402 end;
403
404 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_001,
405     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+06:27:00,
406     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
407     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
408     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
409     KEY, "No_Key")
410
411     command(1,
412     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
413     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
414     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
415 ),
416     command(2,
417     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
418     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
419     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
420 ),
421     note(1,
422     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
423     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
424 ),
425 end;
426
```

```
427 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_001,
428     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+06:29:00,
429     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
430     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
431     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
432     KEY, "No_Key")
433
434     command(1,
435     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
436     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980"\,
437     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
438     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
439     ),
440     command(2,
441     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
442     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
443     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
444     ),
445     note(1,
446     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
447     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.964 Gibit." \
448     ),
449 end;
450
451 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_001,
452     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_057+08:44:00,
453     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
454     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
455     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
456     KEY, "No_Key")
457
458     command(1,
459     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
460     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_001: changing VIR mode into SAFE" \,
461     VIR_SAFE()
462     ),
463     command(2,
464     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
465     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_001: dump the error log information" \,
466     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
467     ),
468     note(1,
469     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
470     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_001: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced" \
471     ),
472 end;
473
474 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_002,
475     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+00:36:16,
476     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
477     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
478     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
479     KEY, "No_Key")
480
481     command(1,
482     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
483     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
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484     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
485   ),
486   command(2,
487     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
488     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_002: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\\,
489     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
490   ),
491   note(1,
492     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
493     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_002: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
494     waiting.\"\\
495   ),
496   end;
497   request(VIR_CSH_C5openCover_002,
498     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+03:37:16,
499     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
500     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
501     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
502     KEY, "No_Key")
503
504   activity(1,
505     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
506     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5openCover_002: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
507     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
508   ),
509   end;
510
511   request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002,
512     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+03:39:16,
513     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
514     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
515     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
516     KEY, "No_Key")
517
518   command(1,
519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
520     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
521     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
522     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
523   ),
524   command(2,
525     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
526     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
527     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
528     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
529   ),
530   command(3,
531     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
532     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
533     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
534     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
535   ),
536   command(4,
537     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
538     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
539     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
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538     ),
539     note(1,
540         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
541         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
542     ),
543     command(5,
544         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
545         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
546         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
547         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
548     ),
549     command(6,
550         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
551         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
552         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
553         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
554     ),
555     command(7,
556         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
557         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
558         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
559         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
560     ),
561     command(8,
562         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
563         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
564         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
565     ),
566     note(2,
567         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
568         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
569     ),
570     command(9,
571         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
572         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
573         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
574         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
575     ),
576     command(10,
577         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
578         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
579         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
580         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
581     ),
582     command(11,
583         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
584         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
585         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
586         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
587     ),
588     command(12,
589         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
590         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
591         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
592     ),
593     note(3,
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590     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
591     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
592     ),
593     command(13,
594     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
595     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
596     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
597     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
598     ),
599     command(14,
600     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
601     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
602     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
603     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
604     ),
605     command(15,
606     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
607     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
608     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
609     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
610     ),
611     command(16,
612     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
613     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
614     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
615     ),
616     note(4,
617     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
618     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\
619     ),
620     command(17,
621     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
622     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
623     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
624     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
625     ),
626     command(18,
627     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
628     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
629     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
630     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
631     ),
632     command(19,
633     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
634     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
635     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
636     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
637     ),
638     command(20,
639     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
640     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
641     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
642     ),
643     note(5,
644     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
645     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\

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642     ),
643     command(21,
644         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
645         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
646         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
647         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
648     ),
649     command(22,
650         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
651         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
652         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
653         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
654     ),
655     command(23,
656         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
657         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
658         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
659         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
660     ),
661     command(24,
662         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
663         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
664         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
665     ),
666     note(6,
667         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
668         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit\"\\
669     ),
670     command(25,
671         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
672         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
673         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
674         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
675     ),
676     command(26,
677         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
678         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
679         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
680         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
681     ),
682     command(27,
683         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
684         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
685         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
686         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
687     ),
688     command(28,
689         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
690         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
691         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
692     ),
693     note(7,
694         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
695         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
696     ),
697     end;

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694
695 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_002,
696         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+06:25:00,
697         TITLE, "VIR close cover",
698         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
699         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
700         KEY, "No_Key")
701
702     activity(1,
703         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
704         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_002: Set for closing the cover." \,
705         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
706     ),
707 end;
708
709 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_002,
710         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+06:27:00,
711         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
712         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
713         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
714         KEY, "No_Key")
715
716     command(1,
717         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
718         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
719         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
720     ),
721     command(2,
722         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
723         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_002: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
724         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
725     ),
726     note(1,
727         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
728         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_002: the cryocooling is off." \
729     ),
730 end;
731
732 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_002,
733         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+06:29:00,
734         TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
735         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
736         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
737         KEY, "No_Key")
738
739     command(1,
740         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
741         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980" \,
742         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
743         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
744     ),
745     command(2,
746         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
747         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
748         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
749     ),
750     note(1,
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751     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
752     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.802 Gibit.\"\
753   ),
754   end;
755
756   request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_002,
757     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_058+08:44:00,
758     TITLE, \"VIR Safe\",
759     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
760     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
761     KEY, \"No_Key\")
762
763   command(1,
764     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
765     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_002: changing VIR mode into SAFE\"\,
766     VIR_SAFE()
767   ),
768   command(2,
769     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
770     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_002: dump the error log information\"\,
771     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG(\"DUMP_LOG\")
772   ),
773   note(1,
774     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
775     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_002: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced\"\
776   ),
777   end;
778
779   request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_003,
780     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+00:36:16,
781     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler on\",
782     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
783     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
784     KEY, \"No_Key\")
785
786   command(1,
787     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
788     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
789     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
790   ),
791   command(2,
792     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
793     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_003: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\,
794     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"CLOSELOOP\",80,0)
795   ),
796   note(1,
797     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
798     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_003: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
799     waiting.\"\
800   ),
801   end;
802
803   request(VIR_CSH_C5openCover_003,
804     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+03:37:16,
805     TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
806     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
807     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
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807     KEY, "No_Key")
808
809     activity(1,
810         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
811         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_003: Set for opening the cover." \,
812         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
813     ),
814 end;
815
816 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003,
817     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+03:39:16,
818     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
819     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
820     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
821     KEY, "No_Key")
822
823     command(1,
824         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
825         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
826         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \,
827         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
828     ),
829     command(2,
830         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
831         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
832         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s" \,
833         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
834     ),
835     command(3,
836         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
837         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020" \,
838         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
839         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
840     ),
841     command(4,
842         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
843         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
844         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
845     ),
846     note(1,
847         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
848         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit" \
849     ),
850     command(5,
851         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
852         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
853         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \,
854         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
855     ),
856     command(6,
857         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
858         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
859         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s" \,
860         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
861     ),
862     command(7,

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859     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
860     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
861     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
862     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
863 ),
864     command(8,
865     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
866     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
867     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
868 ),
869     note(2,
870     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
871     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit\"\\
872 ),
873     command(9,
874     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
875     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
876     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
877     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
878 ),
879     command(10,
880     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
881     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
882     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
883     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
884 ),
885     command(11,
886     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
887     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
888     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
889     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
890 ),
891     command(12,
892     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
893     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
894     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
895 ),
896     note(3,
897     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
898     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\"\\
899 ),
900     command(13,
901     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
902     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
903     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
904     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
905 ),
906     command(14,
907     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
908     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
909     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
910     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
911 ),
912     command(15,
913     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
914     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,

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911     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
912     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
913   ),
914   command(16,
915     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:28:36 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
916     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
917     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
918   ),
919   note(4,
920     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
921     TEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit" \
922   ),
923   command(17,
924     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
925     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
926     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \ ,
927     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
928   ),
929   command(18,
930     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
931     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
932     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s" \ ,
933     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
934   ),
935   command(19,
936     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
937     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020" \ ,
938     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
939     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
940   ),
941   command(20,
942     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:11:56 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
943     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
944     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
945   ),
946   note(5,
947     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
948     TEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit" \
949   ),
950   command(21,
951     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
952     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
953     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \ ,
954     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
955   ),
956   command(22,
957     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
958     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
959     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s" \ ,
960     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
961   ),
962   command(23,
963     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
964     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020" \ ,
965     NTEXT, \ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
966     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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963     ),
964     command(24,
965         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
966         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
967         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
968     ),
969     note(6,
970         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
971         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit\"\\
972     ),
973     command(25,
974         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
975         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
976         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
977         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
978     ),
979     command(26,
980         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
981         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
982         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
983         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
984     ),
985     command(27,
986         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
987         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
988         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
989         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
990     ),
991     command(28,
992         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
993         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
994         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
995     ),
996     note(7,
997         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
998         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
999     ),
1000     end;
1001     request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_003,
1002         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+06:25:00,
1003         TITLE,\"VIR close cover\",
1004         REQUESTOR,\"sfonte\",
1005         PROCESSOR,\"GSC1\",
1006         KEY,\"No_Key\")
1007     activity(1,
1008         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1009         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_003: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
1010         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
1011     ),
1012     end;
1013     request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_003,
1014         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+06:27:00,
1015         TITLE,\"VIR cryocooler off\",
1016         REQUESTOR,\"sfonte\",
```

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1018     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1019     KEY, "No_Key")
1020
1021     command(1,
1022     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1023     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1024     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1025     ),
1026     command(2,
1027     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1028     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_003: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
1029     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
1030     ),
1031     note(1,
1032     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1033     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_003: the cryocooling is off." \
1034     ),
1035 end;
1036
1037 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_003,
1038     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+06:29:00,
1039     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1040     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1041     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1042     KEY, "No_Key")
1043
1044     command(1,
1045     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1046     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980" \,
1047     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
1048     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1049     ),
1050     command(2,
1051     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1052     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1053     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1054     ),
1055     note(1,
1056     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1057     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 2.304 Gibit." \
1058     ),
1059 end;
1060
1061 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_003,
1062     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_059+08:44:00,
1063     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
1064     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1065     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1066     KEY, "No_Key")
1067
1068     command(1,
1069     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1070     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_003: changing VIR mode into SAFE" \,
1071     VIR_SAFE()
1072     ),
1073     command(2,
1074     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1075     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_003: dump the error log information"\,
1076     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
1077   ),
1078   note(1,
1079     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1080     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_003: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\
1081   ),
1082 end;
1083
1084 request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_004,
1085   START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+00:36:16,
1086   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
1087   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1088   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1089   KEY, "No_Key")
1090
1091   command(1,
1092     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1093     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1094     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1095   ),
1096   command(2,
1097     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1098     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_004: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
1099     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
1100   ),
1101   note(1,
1102     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1103     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_004: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
1104     waiting."\"
1105   ),
1106 end;
1107 request(VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_004,
1108   START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+03:37:16,
1109   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1110   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1111   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1112   KEY, "No_Key")
1113
1114   activity(1,
1115     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1116     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_004: Set for opening the cover."\",
1117     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1118   ),
1119 end;
1120
1121 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004,
1122   START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+03:39:16,
1123   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1124   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1125   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1126   KEY, "No_Key")
1127
1128   command(1,
1129     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1130     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1131     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\",
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1131     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1132     ),
1133     command(2,
1134     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1135     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1136     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1137     ),
1138     command(3,
1139     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1140     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1141     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1142     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1143     ),
1144     command(4,
1145     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1146     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1147     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1148     ),
1149     note(1,
1150     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1151     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
1152     ),
1153     command(5,
1154     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1155     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1156     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1157     ),
1158     command(6,
1159     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1160     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1161     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1162     ),
1163     command(7,
1164     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1165     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1166     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1167     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1168     ),
1169     command(8,
1170     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1171     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1172     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1173     ),
1174     note(2,
1175     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1176     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
1177     ),
1178     command(9,
1179     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1180     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1181     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1182     ),

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1183     command(10,  
1184         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1185         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
1186         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
1187     ),  
1188     command(11,  
1189         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1190         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
1191         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
1192         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1193     ),  
1194     command(12,  
1195         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:45:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1196         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1197         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1198     ),  
1199     note(3,  
1200         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1201         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\  
1202     ),  
1203     command(13,  
1204         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1205         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
1206         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
1207     ),  
1208     command(14,  
1209         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1210         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
1211         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
1212     ),  
1213     command(15,  
1214         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1215         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
1216         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
1217         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1218     ),  
1219     command(16,  
1220         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1221         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1222         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1223     ),  
1224     note(4,  
1225         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1226         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\  
1227     ),  
1228     command(17,  
1229         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1230         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
1231         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
1232     ),  
1233     command(18,  
1234         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
```

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1235 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1236 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1237 ),
1238 command(19,
1239 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1240 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1241 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1242 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1243 ),
1244 command(20,
1245 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1246 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1247 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1248 ),
1249 note(5,
1250 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1251 TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\
1252 ),
1253 command(21,
1254 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1255 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1256 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1257 ),
1258 command(22,
1259 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1260 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1261 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1262 ),
1263 command(23,
1264 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1265 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1266 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1267 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1268 ),
1269 command(24,
1270 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1271 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1272 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1273 ),
1274 note(6,
1275 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1276 TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit"\
1277 ),
1278 command(25,
1279 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1280 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1281 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1282 ),
1283 command(26,
1284 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1285 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,

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1286     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1287 ),
1288     command(27,
1289         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1290         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\",\
1291         NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1292         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1293     ),
1294     command(28,
1295         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1296         NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1297         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1298     ),
1299     note(7,
1300         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1301         TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
1302     ),
1303 end;
1304
1305 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_004,
1306     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+06:25:00,
1307     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1308     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1309     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1310     KEY, "No_Key")
1311
1312     activity(1,
1313         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1314         NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_004: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
1315         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1316     ),
1317 end;
1318
1319 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_004,
1320     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+06:27:00,
1321     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
1322     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1323     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1324     KEY, "No_Key")
1325
1326     command(1,
1327         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1328         NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1329         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1330     ),
1331     command(2,
1332         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1333         NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_004: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
1334         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
1335     ),
1336     note(1,
1337         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1338         TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_004: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
1339     ),
1340 end;
1341
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1342 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_004,  
1343     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+06:29:00,  
1344     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
1345     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1346     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1347     KEY, "No_Key")  
1348  
1349     command(1,  
1350         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1351         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980"\,  
1352         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4."\,  
1353         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
1354     ),  
1355     command(2,  
1356         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1357         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
1358         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1359     ),  
1360     note(1,  
1361         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1362         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 3.142 Gibit."\  
1363     ),  
1364 end;  
1365  
1366 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_004,  
1367     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_060+08:44:00,  
1368     TITLE, "VIR Safe",  
1369     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1370     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1371     KEY, "No_Key")  
1372  
1373     command(1,  
1374         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1375         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_004: changing VIR mode into SAFE"\,  
1376         VIR_SAFE()  
1377     ),  
1378     command(2,  
1379         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1380         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_004: dump the error log information"\,  
1381         VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")  
1382     ),  
1383     note(1,  
1384         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1385         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_004: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\  
1386     ),  
1387 end;  
1388  
1389 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_005,  
1390     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+00:36:16,  
1391     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",  
1392     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1393     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1394     KEY, "No_Key")  
1395  
1396     command(1,  
1397         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1398         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
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1399     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1400   ),
1401   command(2,
1402     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1403     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_005: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\\,
1404     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
1405   ),
1406   note(1,
1407     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1408     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_005: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
1409     waiting.\"\\
1410   ),
1411 end;
1412 request(VIR_CSH_C5openCover_005,
1413   START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+03:37:16,
1414   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1415   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1416   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1417   KEY, "No_Key")
1418
1419   activity(1,
1420     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1421     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5openCover_005: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
1422     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1423   ),
1424 end;
1425
1426 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005,
1427   START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+03:39:16,
1428   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1429   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1430   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1431   KEY, "No_Key")
1432
1433   command(1,
1434     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1435     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1436     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
1437     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1438   ),
1439   command(2,
1440     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1441     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1442     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
1443     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1444   ),
1445   command(3,
1446     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1447     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
1448     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1449     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1450   ),
1451   command(4,
1452     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1453     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1454     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()

```

```
1453     ),
1454     note(1,
1455         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1456         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
1457     ),
1458     command(5,
1459         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1460         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1461         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1462         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1463     ),
1464     command(6,
1465         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1466         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1467         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1468         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1469     ),
1470     command(7,
1471         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1472         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1473         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1474         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1475     ),
1476     command(8,
1477         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1478         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1479         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1480     ),
1481     note(2,
1482         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1483         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
1484     ),
1485     command(9,
1486         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1487         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1488         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1489         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1490     ),
1491     command(10,
1492         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1493         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1494         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1495         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1496     ),
1497     command(11,
1498         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1499         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1500         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1501         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1502     ),
1503     command(12,
1504         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1505         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1506         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1507     ),
1508     note(3,
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1505     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1506     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
1507     ),
1508     command(13,
1509     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1510     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1511     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1512     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1513     ),
1514     command(14,
1515     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1516     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1517     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1518     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1519     ),
1520     command(15,
1521     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1522     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1523     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1524     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1525     ),
1526     command(16,
1527     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1528     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1529     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1530     ),
1531     note(4,
1532     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1533     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\
1534     ),
1535     command(17,
1536     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1537     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1538     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1539     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1540     ),
1541     command(18,
1542     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1543     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1544     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1545     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1546     ),
1547     command(19,
1548     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1549     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1550     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1551     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1552     ),
1553     command(20,
1554     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1555     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1556     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1557     ),
1558     note(5,
1559     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1560     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\

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1557     ),
1558     command(21,
1559         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1560         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1561         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1562         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1563     ),
1564     command(22,
1565         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1566         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1567         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1568         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1569     ),
1570     command(23,
1571         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1572         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1573         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1574         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1575     ),
1576     command(24,
1577         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1578         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1579         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1580     ),
1581     note(6,
1582         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1583         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit"\
1584     ),
1585     command(25,
1586         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1587         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1588         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1589         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1590     ),
1591     command(26,
1592         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1593         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1594         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1595         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1596     ),
1597     command(27,
1598         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1599         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1600         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1601         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1602     ),
1603     command(28,
1604         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1605         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1606         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1607     ),
1608     note(7,
1609         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1610         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit"\
1611     ),
1612     end;
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1609
1610 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_005,
1611     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+06:25:00,
1612     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1613     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1614     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1615     KEY, "No_Key")
1616
1617     activity(1,
1618     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1619     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_005: Set for closing the cover." \,
1620     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1621     ),
1622 end;
1623
1624 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_005,
1625     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+06:27:00,
1626     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
1627     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1628     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1629     KEY, "No_Key")
1630
1631     command(1,
1632     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1633     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1634     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1635     ),
1636     command(2,
1637     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1638     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_005: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
1639     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
1640     ),
1641     note(1,
1642     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1643     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_005: the cryocooling is off." \
1644     ),
1645 end;
1646
1647 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_005,
1648     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+06:29:00,
1649     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1650     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1651     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1652     KEY, "No_Key")
1653
1654     command(1,
1655     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1656     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980" \,
1657     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_005: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
1658     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1659     ),
1660     command(2,
1661     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1662     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1663     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1664     ),
1665     note(1,
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1666     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1667     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_005: data volume in VR4 2.751 Gibit.\"\
1668     ),
1669 end;
1670
1671 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_005,
1672     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_061+08:44:00,
1673     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
1674     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1675     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1676     KEY, "No_Key")
1677
1678     command(1,
1679     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1680     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_005: changing VIR mode into SAFE"\,
1681     VIR_SAFE()
1682     ),
1683     command(2,
1684     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1685     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_005: dump the error log information"\,
1686     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
1687     ),
1688     note(1,
1689     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1690     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_005: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\
1691     ),
1692 end;
1693
1694 request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_006,
1695     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+00:36:16,
1696     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
1697     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1698     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1699     KEY, "No_Key")
1700
1701     command(1,
1702     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1703     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
1704     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1705     ),
1706     command(2,
1707     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1708     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_006: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\,
1709     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
1710     ),
1711     note(1,
1712     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1713     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_006: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
1714     waiting.\"\
1715     ),
1716 end;
1717
1717 request(VIR_CSH_C50penCover_006,
1718     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+03:37:16,
1719     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1720     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1721     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
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1722     KEY, "No_Key")
1723
1724     activity(1,
1725         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1726         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_006: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
1727         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1728     ),
1729 end;
1730
1731 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006,
1732     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+03:39:16,
1733     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1734     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1735     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1736     KEY, "No_Key")
1737
1738     command(1,
1739         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1740         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1741         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
1742         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1743     ),
1744     command(2,
1745         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1746         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1747         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
1748         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1749     ),
1750     command(3,
1751         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1752         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
1753         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1754         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1755     ),
1756     command(4,
1757         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1758         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1759         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1760     ),
1761     note(1,
1762         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1763         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit\"\\
1764     ),
1765     command(5,
1766         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1767         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1768         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
1769         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1770     ),
1771     command(6,
1772         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1773         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1774         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
1775         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1776     ),
1777     command(7,

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1774     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1775     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
1776     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1777     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1778     ),
1779     command(8,
1780     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1781     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1782     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1783     ),
1784     note(2,
1785     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1786     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit\"\\
1787     ),
1788     command(9,
1789     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1790     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1791     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
1792     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1793     ),
1794     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1795     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1796     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
1797     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
1798     ),
1799     command(11,
1800     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1801     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
1802     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1803     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1804     ),
1805     command(12,
1806     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1807     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1808     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1809     ),
1810     note(3,
1811     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1812     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\"\\
1813     ),
1814     command(13,
1815     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1816     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1817     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
1818     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1819     ),
1820     command(14,
1821     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1822     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1823     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
1824     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
1825     ),
1826     command(15,
1827     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1828     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,

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1826     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1827     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1828   ),
1829   command(16,
1830     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1831     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1832     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1833   ),
1834   note(4,
1835     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1836     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\
1837   ),
1838   command(17,
1839     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1840     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1841     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1842     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1843   ),
1844   command(18,
1845     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1846     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1847     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1848     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1849   ),
1850   command(19,
1851     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1852     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1853     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1854     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1855   ),
1856   command(20,
1857     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1858     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1859     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1860   ),
1861   note(5,
1862     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1863     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\
1864   ),
1865   command(21,
1866     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1867     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1868     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
1869     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1870   ),
1871   command(22,
1872     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1873     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1874     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
1875     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
1876   ),
1877   command(23,
1878     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1879     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
1880     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1881     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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1878     ),
1879     command(24,
1880         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1881         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1882         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1883     ),
1884     note(6,
1885         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1886         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit\"\\
1887     ),
1888     command(25,
1889         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1890         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
1891         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
1892         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
1893     ),
1894     command(26,
1895         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1896         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
1897         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
1898         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
1899     ),
1900     command(27,
1901         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1902         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
1903         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1904         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1905     ),
1906     command(28,
1907         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1908         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1909         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1910     ),
1911     note(7,
1912         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1913         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
1914     ),
1915     end;
1916     request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_006,
1917         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+06:25:00,
1918         TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
1919         REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1920         PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1921         KEY, \"No_Key\")
1922     activity(1,
1923         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1924         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_006: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
1925         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
1926     ),
1927     end;
1928     request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_006,
1929         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+06:27:00,
1930         TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
1931         REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",

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1933     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1934     KEY, "No_Key")
1935
1936     command(1,
1937     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1938     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1939     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1940     ),
1941     command(2,
1942     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1943     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_006: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
1944     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
1945     ),
1946     note(1,
1947     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1948     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_006: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
1949     ),
1950 end;
1951
1952 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_006,
1953     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+06:29:00,
1954     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1955     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1956     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1957     KEY, "No_Key")
1958
1959     command(1,
1960     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1961     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980\"\\,
1962     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_006: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1963     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1964     ),
1965     command(2,
1966     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1967     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1968     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1969     ),
1970     note(1,
1971     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1972     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_006: data volume in VR4 3.589 Gibit.\"\\
1973     ),
1974 end;
1975
1976 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_006,
1977     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_062+08:44:00,
1978     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
1979     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1980     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1981     KEY, "No_Key")
1982
1983     command(1,
1984     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1985     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_006: changing VIR mode into SAFE\"\\,
1986     VIR_SAFE()
1987     ),
1988     command(2,
1989     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1990     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_006: dump the error log information"\,
1991     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
1992   ),
1993   note(1,
1994     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1995     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_006: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\
1996   ),
1997   end;
1998
1999   request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_007,
2000     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+00:36:16,
2001     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
2002     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2003     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2004     KEY, "No_Key")
2005
2006   command(1,
2007     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2008     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2009     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2010   ),
2011   command(2,
2012     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2013     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_007: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
2014     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
2015   ),
2016   note(1,
2017     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2018     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_007: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
2019     waiting."\"
2020   ),
2021   end;
2022
2023   request(VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_007,
2024     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+03:37:16,
2025     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
2026     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2027     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2028     KEY, "No_Key")
2029
2030   activity(1,
2031     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2032     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_007: Set for opening the cover."\",
2033     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
2034   ),
2035   end;
2036
2037   request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007,
2038     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+03:39:16,
2039     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
2040     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2041     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2042     KEY, "No_Key")
2043
2044   command(1,
2045     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2046     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2047     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\"
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2046     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2047     ),
2048     command(2,
2049     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2050     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2051     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2052     ),
2053     command(3,
2054     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2055     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2056     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2057     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2058     ),
2059     command(4,
2060     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2061     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2062     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2063     ),
2064     note(1,
2065     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2066     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
2067     ),
2068     command(5,
2069     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2070     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2071     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2072     ),
2073     command(6,
2074     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2075     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2076     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2077     ),
2078     command(7,
2079     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2080     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2081     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2082     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2083     ),
2084     command(8,
2085     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2086     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2087     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2088     ),
2089     note(2,
2090     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2091     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
2092     ),
2093     command(9,
2094     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2095     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2096     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2097     ),

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2098     command(10,  
2099         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2100         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
2101         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
2102     ),  
2103     command(11,  
2104         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2105         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
2106         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
2107         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
2108     ),  
2109     command(12,  
2110         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2111         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
2112         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
2113     ),  
2114     note(3,  
2115         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2116         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\  
2117     ),  
2118     command(13,  
2119         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2120         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
2121         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
2122     ),  
2123     command(14,  
2124         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2125         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
2126         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
2127     ),  
2128     command(15,  
2129         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2130         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
2131         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
2132         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
2133     ),  
2134     command(16,  
2135         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2136         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
2137         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
2138     ),  
2139     note(4,  
2140         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2141         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\  
2142     ),  
2143     command(17,  
2144         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2145         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
2146         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
2147     ),  
2148     command(18,  
2149         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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2150 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2151 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2152 ),
2153 command(19,
2154 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2155 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2156 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2157 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2158 ),
2159 command(20,
2160 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:57:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2161 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2162 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2163 ),
2164 note(5,
2165 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2166 TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\
2167 ),
2168 command(21,
2169 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2170 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2171 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2172 ),
2173 command(22,
2174 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2175 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2176 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2177 ),
2178 command(23,
2179 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2180 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2181 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2182 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2183 ),
2184 command(24,
2185 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2186 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2187 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2188 ),
2189 note(6,
2190 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2191 TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit"\
2192 ),
2193 command(25,
2194 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2195 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2196 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2197 ),
2198 command(26,
2199 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2200 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,

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2201     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2202     ),
2203     command(27,
2204     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2205     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\",\
2206     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
2207     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2208     ),
2209     command(28,
2210     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2211     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2212     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2213     ),
2214     note(7,
2215     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2216     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_007: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
2217     ),
2218 end;
2219
2220 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_007,
2221     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+06:25:00,
2222     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
2223     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2224     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2225     KEY, "No_Key")
2226
2227     activity(1,
2228     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2229     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_007: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
2230     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
2231     ),
2232 end;
2233
2234 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_007,
2235     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+06:27:00,
2236     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
2237     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2238     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2239     KEY, "No_Key")
2240
2241     command(1,
2242     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2243     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2244     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2245     ),
2246     command(2,
2247     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2248     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_007: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
2249     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
2250     ),
2251     note(1,
2252     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2253     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_007: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
2254     ),
2255 end;
2256
```

```
2257 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_007,  
2258     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+06:29:00,  
2259     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
2260     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
2261     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
2262     KEY, "No_Key")  
2263  
2264     command(1,  
2265         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2266         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980"\,  
2267         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_007: begin data dumping into VR4."\,  
2268         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
2269     ),  
2270     command(2,  
2271         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2272         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
2273         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
2274     ),  
2275     note(1,  
2276         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2277         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_007: data volume in VR4 4.192 Gibit."\  
2278     ),  
2279 end;  
2280  
2281 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_007,  
2282     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_063+08:44:00,  
2283     TITLE, "VIR Safe",  
2284     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
2285     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
2286     KEY, "No_Key")  
2287  
2288     command(1,  
2289         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2290         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_007: changing VIR mode into SAFE"\,  
2291         VIR_SAFE()  
2292     ),  
2293     command(2,  
2294         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2295         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_007: dump the error log information"\,  
2296         VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")  
2297     ),  
2298     note(1,  
2299         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2300         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_007: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\  
2301     ),  
2302 end;  
2303  
2304 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_008,  
2305     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+00:36:16,  
2306     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",  
2307     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
2308     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
2309     KEY, "No_Key")  
2310  
2311     command(1,  
2312         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2313         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
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2314     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2315 ),
2316     command(2,
2317         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2318         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_008: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\\,
2319         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
2320     ),
2321     note(1,
2322         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2323         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_008: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
2324         waiting.\"\\
2325     ),
2326 end;
2327 request(VIR_CSH_C5openCover_008,
2328     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+03:37:16,
2329     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
2330     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2331     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2332     KEY, "No_Key")
2333
2334     activity(1,
2335         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2336         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5openCover_008: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
2337         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
2338     ),
2339 end;
2340
2341 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008,
2342     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+03:39:16,
2343     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
2344     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2345     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2346     KEY, "No_Key")
2347
2348     command(1,
2349         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2350         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2351         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
2352         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2353     ),
2354     command(2,
2355         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2356         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2357         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
2358         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2359     ),
2360     command(3,
2361         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2362         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
2363         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2364         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2365     ),
2366     command(4,
2367         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2368         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2369         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()

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2368     ),
2369     note(1,
2370         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2371         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
2372     ),
2373     command(5,
2374         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2375         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2376         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2377         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2378     ),
2379     command(6,
2380         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2381         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2382         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2383         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2384     ),
2385     command(7,
2386         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2387         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2388         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2389         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2390     ),
2391     command(8,
2392         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2393         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2394         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2395     ),
2396     note(2,
2397         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2398         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
2399     ),
2400     command(9,
2401         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2402         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2403         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2404         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2405     ),
2406     command(10,
2407         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2408         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2409         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2410         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2411     ),
2412     command(11,
2413         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2414         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2415         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2416         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2417     ),
2418     command(12,
2419         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:51:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2420         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2421         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2422     ),
2423     note(3,
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2420     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2421     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
2422     ),
2423     command(13,
2424     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2425     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2426     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2427     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2428     ),
2429     command(14,
2430     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2431     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2432     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2433     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2434     ),
2435     command(15,
2436     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2437     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2438     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2439     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2440     ),
2441     command(16,
2442     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2443     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2444     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2445     ),
2446     note(4,
2447     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2448     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\
2449     ),
2450     command(17,
2451     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2452     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2453     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2454     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2455     ),
2456     command(18,
2457     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2458     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2459     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2460     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2461     ),
2462     command(19,
2463     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2464     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2465     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2466     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2467     ),
2468     command(20,
2469     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2470     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2471     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2472     ),
2473     note(5,
2474     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2475     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\

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2472     ),
2473     command(21,
2474         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2475         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2476         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2477         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2478     ),
2479     command(22,
2480         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2481         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2482         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2483         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2484     ),
2485     command(23,
2486         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2487         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2488         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2489         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2490     ),
2491     command(24,
2492         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:40:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2493         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2494         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2495     ),
2496     note(6,
2497         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2498         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit\"\\
2499     ),
2500     command(25,
2501         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2502         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2503         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2504         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2505     ),
2506     command(26,
2507         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2508         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2509         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2510         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2511     ),
2512     command(27,
2513         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2514         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2515         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2516         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2517     ),
2518     command(28,
2519         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2520         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2521         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2522     ),
2523     note(7,
2524         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2525         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_008: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
2526     ),
2527     end;

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2524
2525 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_008,
2526     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+06:25:00,
2527     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
2528     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2529     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2530     KEY, "No_Key")
2531
2532     activity(1,
2533         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2534         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_008: Set for closing the cover."\\,
2535         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
2536     ),
2537 end;
2538
2539 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_008,
2540     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+06:27:00,
2541     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
2542     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2543     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2544     KEY, "No_Key")
2545
2546     command(1,
2547         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2548         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2549         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2550     ),
2551     command(2,
2552         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2553         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_008: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\\,
2554         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
2555     ),
2556     note(1,
2557         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2558         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_008: the cryocooling is off."\\
2559     ),
2560 end;
2561
2562 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_008,
2563     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+06:29:00,
2564     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
2565     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2566     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2567     KEY, "No_Key")
2568
2569     command(1,
2570         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2571         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980"\\,
2572         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_008: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
2573         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
2574     ),
2575     command(2,
2576         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2577         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2578         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2579     ),
2580     note(1,
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2581     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2582     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_008: data volume in VR4 4.055 Gibit.\"\
2583   ),
2584 end;
2585
2586 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_008,
2587     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_064+08:44:00,
2588     TITLE, \"VIR Safe\",
2589     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2590     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
2591     KEY, \"No_Key\")
2592
2593     command(1,
2594     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2595     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_008: changing VIR mode into SAFE\"\,
2596     VIR_SAFE()
2597   ),
2598     command(2,
2599     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2600     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_008: dump the error log information\"\,
2601     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG(\"DUMP_LOG\")
2602   ),
2603     note(1,
2604     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2605     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_008: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced\"\
2606   ),
2607 end;
2608
2609 request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_009,
2610     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_065+00:36:16,
2611     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler on\",
2612     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2613     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
2614     KEY, \"No_Key\")
2615
2616     command(1,
2617     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2618     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
2619     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2620   ),
2621     command(2,
2622     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2623     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_009: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\,
2624     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"CLOSELOOP\",80,0)
2625   ),
2626     note(1,
2627     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2628     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_009: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
2629     waiting.\"\
2630   ),
2630 end;
2631
2632 request(VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_009,
2633     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_065+03:37:16,
2634     TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
2635     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2636     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
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2637     KEY, "No_Key")
2638
2639     activity(1,
2640         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2641         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5OpenCover_009: Set for opening the cover."\,
2642         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
2643     ),
2644 end;
2645
2646 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009,
2647     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_065+03:39:16,
2648     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
2649     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2650     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2651     KEY, "No_Key")
2652
2653     command(1,
2654         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2655         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2656         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2657         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2658     ),
2659     command(2,
2660         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2661         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2662         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2663         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2664     ),
2665     command(3,
2666         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2667         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2668         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2669         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2670     ),
2671     command(4,
2672         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2673         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
2674         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2675     ),
2676     note(1,
2677         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2678         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
2679     ),
2680     command(5,
2681         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2682         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2683         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2684         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2685     ),
2686     command(6,
2687         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2688         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2689         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2690         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2691     ),
2692     command(7,

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2689     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2690     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
2691     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2692     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2693     ),
2694     command(8,
2695     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2696     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2697     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2698     ),
2699     note(2,
2700     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2701     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit\"\\
2702     ),
2703     command(9,
2704     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2705     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2706     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
2707     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2708     ),
2709     command(10,
2710     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2711     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2712     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
2713     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
2714     ),
2715     command(11,
2716     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2717     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
2718     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2719     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2720     ),
2721     command(12,
2722     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2723     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2724     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2725     ),
2726     note(3,
2727     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2728     TEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\"\\
2729     ),
2730     command(13,
2731     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2732     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2733     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
2734     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2735     ),
2736     command(14,
2737     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2738     NTEXT,\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2739     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
2740     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
2741     ),
2742     command(15,
2743     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2744     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,

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2741     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2742     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2743   ),
2744   command(16,
2745     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2746     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2747     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2748   ),
2749   note(4,
2750     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2751     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\
2752   ),
2753   command(17,
2754     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2755     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2756     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2757     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2758   ),
2759   command(18,
2760     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2761     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2762     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2763     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2764   ),
2765   command(19,
2766     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2767     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2768     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2769     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2770   ),
2771   command(20,
2772     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2773     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2774     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2775   ),
2776   note(5,
2777     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2778     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\
2779   ),
2780   command(21,
2781     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2782     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2783     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2784     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2785   ),
2786   command(22,
2787     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2788     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2789     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2790     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2791   ),
2792   command(23,
2793     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2794     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2795     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2796     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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2793     ),
2794     command(24,
2795         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2796         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2797         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2798     ),
2799     note(6,
2800         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2801         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit\"\\
2802     ),
2803     command(25,
2804         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2805         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2806         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
2807         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2808     ),
2809     command(26,
2810         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2811         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2812         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
2813         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
2814     ),
2815     command(27,
2816         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2817         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
2818         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2819         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2820     ),
2821     command(28,
2822         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2823         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2824         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2825     ),
2826     note(7,
2827         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2828         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_009: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit\"\\
2829     ),
2830     end;
2831     request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_009,
2832         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_065+06:25:00,
2833         TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
2834         REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2835         PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
2836         KEY, \"No_Key\")
2837     activity(1,
2838         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2839         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_009: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
2840         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
2841     ),
2842     end;
2843     request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_009,
2844         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_065+06:27:00,
2845         TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
2846         REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
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2848     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2849     KEY, "No_Key")
2850
2851     command(1,
2852     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2853     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2854     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2855     ),
2856     command(2,
2857     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2858     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_009: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
2859     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
2860     ),
2861     note(1,
2862     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2863     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_009: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
2864     ),
2865 end;
2866
2867 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_009,
2868     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_065+06:29:00,
2869     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
2870     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2871     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2872     KEY, "No_Key")
2873
2874     command(1,
2875     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2876     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_009: changing VIR mode into SAFE\"\\,
2877     VIR_SAFE()
2878     ),
2879     command(2,
2880     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2881     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_009: dump the error log information\"\\,
2882     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
2883     ),
2884     note(1,
2885     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2886     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_009: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced\"\\
2887     ),
2888 end;
2889
2890 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_010,
2891     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+00:36:16,
2892     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
2893     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2894     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2895     KEY, "No_Key")
2896
2897     command(1,
2898     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2899     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2900     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2901     ),
2902     command(2,
2903     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2904     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_010: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\\,
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2905     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)
2906   ),
2907   note(1,
2908     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2909     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_010: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
2910     waiting." \
2911   ),
2912   end;
2913   request(VIR_CSH_C5openCover_010,
2914     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+03:37:16,
2915     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
2916     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2917     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2918     KEY, "No_Key")
2919
2920   activity(1,
2921     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2922     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5openCover_010: Set for opening the cover." \,
2923     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
2924   ),
2925   end;
2926
2927   request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010,
2928     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+03:39:16,
2929     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
2930     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2931     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2932     KEY, "No_Key")
2933
2934   command(1,
2935     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2936     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
2937     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \,
2938     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2939   ),
2940   command(2,
2941     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2942     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
2943     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s" \,
2944     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2945   ),
2946   command(3,
2947     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2948     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020" \,
2949     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
2950     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2951   ),
2952   command(4,
2953     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2954     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
2955     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2956   ),
2957   note(1,
2958     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2959     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit" \
2960   ),
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2959     command(5,
2960         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2961         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
                SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2962         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2963     ),
2964     command(6,
2965         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2966         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
                frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2967         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2968     ),
2969     command(7,
2970         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2971         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2972         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2973         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2974     ),
2975     command(8,
2976         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2977         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2978         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2979     ),
2980     note(2,
2981         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2982         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit"\
2983     ),
2984     command(9,
2985         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2986         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
                SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
2987         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
2988     ),
2989     command(10,
2990         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2991         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
                frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
2992         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
2993     ),
2994     command(11,
2995         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2996         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
2997         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2998         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2999     ),
3000     command(12,
3001         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3002         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3003         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3004     ),
3005     note(3,
3006         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3007         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
3008     ),
3009     command(13,
3010         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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3011 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
3012 SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\  
3013 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
3014 ),  
3015 command(14,  
3016 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3017 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
3018 frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\  
3019 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
3020 ),  
3021 command(15,  
3022 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3023 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\  
3024 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
3025 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
3026 ),  
3027 command(16,  
3028 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3029 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
3030 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
3031 ),  
3032 note(4,  
3033 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3034 TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\  
3035 ),  
3036 command(17,  
3037 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3038 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
3039 SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\  
3040 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
3041 ),  
3042 command(18,  
3043 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3044 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
3045 frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\  
3046 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
3047 ),  
3048 command(19,  
3049 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3050 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\  
3051 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
3052 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
3053 ),  
3054 command(20,  
3055 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3056 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
3057 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
3058 ),  
3059 note(5,  
3060 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3061 TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\  
3062 ),  
3063 command(21,  
3064 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3065 NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
3066 SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\  
3067 )
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3062     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3063     ),
3064     command(22,
3065     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3066     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3067     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3068     ),
3069     command(23,
3070     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3071     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3072     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3073     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3074     ),
3075     command(24,
3076     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3077     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
3078     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3079     ),
3080     note(6,
3081     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3082     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit"\
3083     ),
3084     command(25,
3085     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3086     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3087     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3088     ),
3089     command(26,
3090     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3091     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3092     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3093     ),
3094     command(27,
3095     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3096     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3097     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3098     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3099     ),
3100     command(28,
3101     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3102     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
3103     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3104     ),
3105     note(7,
3106     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3107     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_010: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit"\
3108     ),
3109     end;
3110
3111     request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_010,
3112     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+06:25:00,
3113     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
3114     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",

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3115     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3116     KEY, "No_Key")
3117
3118     activity(1,
3119     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3120     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_010: Set for closing the cover."\\,
3121     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
3122     ),
3123 end;
3124
3125 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_010,
3126     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+06:27:00,
3127     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
3128     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3129     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3130     KEY, "No_Key")
3131
3132     command(1,
3133     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3134     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
3135     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3136     ),
3137     command(2,
3138     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3139     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_010: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\\,
3140     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
3141     ),
3142     note(1,
3143     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3144     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_010: the cryocooling is off."\\
3145     ),
3146 end;
3147
3148 request(VIR_CSH_C5PartialDumpDataToVR4_010,
3149     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+06:29:00,
3150     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
3151     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3152     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3153     KEY, "No_Key")
3154
3155     command(1,
3156     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3157     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980"\\,
3158     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PartialDumpDataToVR4_010: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
3159     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
3160     ),
3161     command(2,
3162     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3163     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PartialDumpDataToVR4_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
3164     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3165     ),
3166     note(1,
3167     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3168     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PartialDumpDataToVR4_010: data volume in VR4 4.086 Gibit."\\
3169     ),
3170 end;
3171
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3172 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_010,  
3173     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_066+08:59:10,  
3174     TITLE, "VIR Safe",  
3175     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
3176     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
3177     KEY, "No_Key")  
3178  
3179     command(1,  
3180         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
3181         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_010: changing VIR mode into SAFE"\,  
3182         VIR_SAFE()  
3183     ),  
3184     command(2,  
3185         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3186         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_010: dump the error log information"\,  
3187         VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")  
3188     ),  
3189     note(1,  
3190         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3191         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_010: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\  
3192     ),  
3193 end;  
3194  
3195 request(VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_011,  
3196     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_067+00:36:16,  
3197     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",  
3198     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
3199     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
3200     KEY, "No_Key")  
3201  
3202     command(1,  
3203         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
3204         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
3205         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
3206     ),  
3207     command(2,  
3208         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3209         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_011: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\  
3210         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",80,0)  
3211     ),  
3212     note(1,  
3213         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3214         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Cryocooler0n_011: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour  
3215         waiting."\  
3216     ),  
3217 end;  
3218  
3219 request(VIR_CSH_C5openCover_011,  
3220     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_067+03:37:16,  
3221     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
3222     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
3223     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
3224     KEY, "No_Key")  
3225  
3226     activity(1,  
3227         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
3228         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5openCover_011: Set for opening the cover."\  
3229     ),  
3230 end;
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3228     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
3229     ),
3230 end;
3231
3232 request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011,
3233     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_067+03:39:16,
3234     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
3235     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3236     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3237     KEY, "No_Key")
3238
3239     command(1,
3240     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3241     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3242     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3243     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3244     ),
3245     command(2,
3246     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3247     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3248     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3249     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3250     ),
3251     command(3,
3252     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3253     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3254     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3255     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3256     ),
3257     command(4,
3258     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3259     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3260     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3261     ),
3262     note(1,
3263     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3264     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.118 Gibit"\
3265     ),
3266     command(5,
3267     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3268     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3269     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3270     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3271     ),
3272     command(6,
3273     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3274     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3275     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3276     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3277     ),
3278     command(7,
3279     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3280     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3281     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3282     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3283     ),
3284     )

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3280     command(8,
3281         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3282         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
3283         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3284     ),
3285     note(2,
3286         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3287         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.237 Gibit\"\\
3288     ),
3289     command(9,
3290         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3291         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3292         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
3293         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3294     ),
3295     command(10,
3296         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3297         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3298         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
3299         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
3300     ),
3301     command(11,
3302         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3303         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
3304         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
3305         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
3306     ),
3307     command(12,
3308         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3309         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
3310         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3311     ),
3312     note(3,
3313         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3314         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\"\\
3315     ),
3316     command(13,
3317         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3318         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3319         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
3320         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3321     ),
3322     command(14,
3323         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3324         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3325         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s\"\\,
3326         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"N
3327     ),
3328     command(15,
3329         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3330         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020\"\\,
3331         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
3332         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
3333     ),
3334     command(16,
3335         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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3332     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
3333     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3334   ),
3335   note(4,
3336     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3337     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.473 Gibit"\\
3338   ),
3339   command(17,
3340     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3341     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3342     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\\,
3343     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3344   ),
3345   command(18,
3346     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3347     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3348     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\\,
3349     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3350   ),
3351   command(19,
3352     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3353     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\\,
3354     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
3355     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3356   ),
3357   command(20,
3358     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3359     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
3360     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3361   ),
3362   note(5,
3363     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3364     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.591 Gibit"\\
3365   ),
3366   command(21,
3367     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3368     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3369     SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\\,
3370     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3371   ),
3372   command(22,
3373     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3374     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3375     frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\\,
3376     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3377   ),
3378   command(23,
3379     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3380     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\\,
3381     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
3382     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3383   ),
3384   command(24,
3385     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3386     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
3387     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()

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3384     ),
3385     note(6,
3386         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3387         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.710 Gibit"\
3388     ),
3389     command(25,
3390         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3391         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3392         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3393         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3394     ),
3395     command(26,
3396         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3397         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3398         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3399         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3400     ),
3401     command(27,
3402         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3403         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3404         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3405         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3406     ),
3407     command(28,
3408         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3409         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3410         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3411     ),
3412     note(7,
3413         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3414         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_011: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.828 Gibit"\
3415     ),
3416 end;
3417
3418 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_011,
3419     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_067+06:25:00,
3420     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
3421     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3422     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3423     KEY, "No_Key")
3424
3425 activity(1,
3426     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3427     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_011: Set for closing the cover.""\,
3428     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
3429     ),
3430 end;
3431
3432 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_011,
3433     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_067+06:27:00,
3434     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
3435     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3436     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3437     KEY, "No_Key")
3438
3439 command(1,
3440     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,

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3439     NTEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_011: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
3440     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3441   ),
3442   command(2,
3443     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3444     NTEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_011: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
3445     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN( \"OFF\", 75, 2500)
3446   ),
3447   note(1,
3448     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3449     TEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_011: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
3450   ),
3451 end;
3452
3453 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_011,
3454   START_TIME, CSH_DLTERM_067+06:29:00,
3455   TITLE, \"VIR Safe\",
3456   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
3457   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
3458   KEY, \"No_Key\")
3459
3460   command(1,
3461     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
3462     NTEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_011: changing VIR mode into SAFE\"\\,
3463     VIR_SAFE()
3464   ),
3465   command(2,
3466     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:01:00\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3467     NTEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_011: dump the error log information\"\\,
3468     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG( \"DUMP_LOG\")
3469   ),
3470   note(1,
3471     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:01:00\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3472     TEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_011: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced\"\\
3473   ),
3474 end;
3475
3476 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_012,
3477   START_TIME, CSH_DLTERM_068+00:36:16,
3478   TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler on\",
3479   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
3480   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
3481   KEY, \"No_Key\")
3482
3483   command(1,
3484     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
3485     NTEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
3486     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3487   ),
3488   command(2,
3489     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3490     NTEXT, \"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_012: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\"\\,
3491     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN( \"CLOSELOOP\", 80, 0)
3492   ),
3493   note(1,
3494     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\03:00:00\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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3495     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOn_012: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
3496         ),
3497     end;
3498
3499     request(VIR_CSH_C50penCover_012,
3500         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+03:37:16,
3501         TITLE, "VIR open cover",
3502         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3503         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3504         KEY, "No_Key")
3505
3506     activity(1,
3507         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3508         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C50penCover_012: Set for opening the cover." \,
3509         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
3510     ),
3511     end;
3512
3513     request(VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012,
3514         START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+03:39:16,
3515         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
3516         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3517         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3518         KEY, "No_Key")
3519
3520     command(1,
3521         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3522         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3523         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \,
3524         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3525     ),
3526     command(2,
3527         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3528         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
3529         frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s" \,
3530         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3531     ),
3532     command(3,
3533         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3534         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020" \,
3535         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
3536         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3537     ),
3538     command(4,
3539         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3540         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
3541         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3542     ),
3543     note(1,
3544         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3545         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.946 Gibit" \
3546     ),
3547     command(5,
3548         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3549         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
3550         SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps" \,

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3548     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3549     ),
3550     command(6,
3551     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3552     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3553     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3554     ),
3555     command(7,
3556     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3557     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3558     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3559     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3560     ),
3561     command(8,
3562     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3563     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3564     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3565     ),
3566     note(2,
3567     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3568     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 1.065 Gibit"\
3569     ),
3570     command(9,
3571     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3572     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3573     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3574     ),
3575     command(10,
3576     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3577     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3578     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3579     ),
3580     command(11,
3581     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3582     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3583     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3584     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3585     ),
3586     command(12,
3587     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3588     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3589     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3590     ),
3591     note(3,
3592     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3593     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 1.183 Gibit"\
3594     ),
3595     command(13,
3596     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3597     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3598     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3599     ),

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3600     command(14,  
3601         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3602         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
          frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
3603         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
3604     ),  
3605     command(15,  
3606         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3607         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
3608         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
3609         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
3610     ),  
3611     command(16,  
3612         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3613         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
3614         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
3615     ),  
3616     note(4,  
3617         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3618         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 1.301 Gibit"\  
3619     ),  
3620     command(17,  
3621         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3622         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
          SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
3623         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
3624     ),  
3625     command(18,  
3626         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3627         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
          frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,  
3628         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N  
3629     ),  
3630     command(19,  
3631         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3632         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,  
3633         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
3634         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
3635     ),  
3636     command(20,  
3637         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3638         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
3639         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
3640     ),  
3641     note(5,  
3642         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3643         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 1.419 Gibit"\  
3644     ),  
3645     command(21,  
3646         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3647         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,  
          SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,  
3648         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)  
3649     ),  
3650     command(22,  
3651         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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3652     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
        frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3653     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3654     ),
3655     command(23,
3656     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3657     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3658     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3659     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3660     ),
3661     command(24,
3662     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:56\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3663     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3664     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3665     ),
3666     note(6,
3667     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3668     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.538 Gibit"\
3669     ),
3670     command(25,
3671     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3672     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: SP_MODE_10_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_10_END_ALFA,
        SP_MODE_10_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
3673     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,38,39,40,562500,562500,4500)
3674     ),
3675     command(26,
3676     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3677     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
        frame,10 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=7.500s"\,
3678     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",10,67,110,137,375,5,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
3679     ),
3680     command(27,
3681     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3682     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.020"\,
3683     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
3684     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
3685     ),
3686     command(28,
3687     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:23:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3688     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
3689     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3690     ),
3691     note(7,
3692     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3693     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5PushbroomToVIR_012: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.656 Gibit"\
3694     ),
3695 end;
3696
3697 request(VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_012,
3698     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+06:25:00,
3699     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
3700     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3701     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3702     KEY, "No_Key")
3703
3704     activity(1,

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3705     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
3706     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CloseCover_012: Set for closing the cover."\  
3707     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
3708     ),  
3709 end;  
3710  
3711 request(VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_012,  
3712     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+06:27:00,  
3713     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",  
3714     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
3715     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
3716     KEY, "No_Key")  
3717  
3718     command(1,  
3719     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
3720     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
3721     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
3722     ),  
3723     command(2,  
3724     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3725     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_012: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\  
3726     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)  
3727     ),  
3728     note(1,  
3729     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3730     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5CryocoolerOff_012: the cryocooling is off."\  
3731     ),  
3732 end;  
3733  
3734 request(VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_012,  
3735     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+06:29:00,  
3736     TITLE, "VIR Safe",  
3737     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
3738     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
3739     KEY, "No_Key")  
3740  
3741     command(1,  
3742     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
3743     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_012: changing VIR mode into SAFE"\  
3744     VIR_SAFE()  
3745     ),  
3746     command(2,  
3747     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3748     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_012: dump the error log information"\  
3749     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")  
3750     ),  
3751     note(1,  
3752     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
3753     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5SAFEmode_012: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\  
3754     ),  
3755 end;  
3756  
3757 request(VIR_CSH_C5Standby_012,  
3758     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+42:42:00,  
3759     TITLE, "VIR Stand_By",  
3760     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
3761     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
```

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3762     KEY, "No_Key")
3763
3764     command(1,
3765     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3766     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5Standby_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
3767     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3768     ),
3769 end;
3770
3771 request(VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_012,
3772     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+42:43:00,
3773     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
3774     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3775     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3776     KEY, "No_Key")
3777
3778     command(1,
3779     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3780     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.980"\,
3781     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_012: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
3782     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
3783     ),
3784     command(2,
3785     SCHEDULED_TIME,\08:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3786     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_012: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
3787     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
3788     ),
3789     note(1,
3790     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
3791     TEXT,\\"VIR_CSH_C5DumpDataToVR4_012: data volume in VR4 0.000 Gibit."\
3792     ),
3793 end;
3794
3795 request(VIR_CSH_VMLEND_C5HAMO,
3796     START_TIME,CSH_DLTERM_068+51:44:00,
3797     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_csh_C5HAMO (ds713)",
3798     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
3799     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
3800     KEY, "No_Key")
3801
3802     note(1,
3803     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
3804     TEXT,\\"END OF SEQUENCE: ds713 - vir_csh_C5HAMO"\
3805     ),
3806 end;
3807
3808 $$EOF
```